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THERAPY

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*Учредитель Бухарский государственный
медицинский институт имени Абу Али ибн Сино*

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Адрес редакции:

Республика Узбекистан, 200100,
г. Бухара, ул. А. Гиждувани, 23.

Телефон:

(99865) 223-00-50

Факс

(99866) 223-00-50

Сайт

<https://ivit.uz/>

e-mail

shnaimova5@gmail.com

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NEW MARKER OF DIAGNOSIS OF CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASES

N.O.Giyosova, L.B.Sarvarova

**Bukhara state medical institute, Department of hematology and clinical
laboratory diagnostics**

Annotation:

Uromodulin, encoded by the UMOD gene, is a key player in renal physiology, particularly in the formation and function of Tam Harsfall protein. This article provides an in-depth exploration of the UMOD gene, shedding light on its structure, regulation, and the multifaceted roles of uromodulin in renal health. The review delves into recent advancements in our understanding of the molecular mechanisms underlying uromodulin's involvement in renal function, including its impact on electrolyte homeostasis, immune response modulation, and its potential implications in various renal disorders.

Furthermore, this article highlights recent research findings and breakthroughs in the field, emphasizing studies published after 2015. The discussion encompasses novel insights into the genetic variations within the UMOD gene and their associations with renal diseases, as well as emerging therapeutic strategies targeting uromodulin-related conditions. Additionally, the article explores the potential diagnostic and prognostic applications of uromodulin in renal disorders, offering a comprehensive overview of the current state of knowledge in this rapidly evolving field.

Keywords: *Tam Harsfall protein, Uromodulin, Gene UMOD, Renal function, Biomarker, Kidney disorders.*

НОВЫЙ МАРКЕР ДИАГНОСТИКИ ХРОНИЧЕСКИХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ПОЧЕК

Н.О.Гиёсова, Л.Б.Сарварова, Ислам Сибгха

**Бухарский государственный медицинский институт, Кафедры
гематологии и клинической лабораторной диагностики**

Аннотация:

Уромодулин, кодируемый геном UMOD, играет ключевую роль в физиологии почек, особенно в образовании и функционировании белка Там-Харсфолла. В этой статье представлено углубленное исследование гена UMOD, проливающее свет на его структуру, регуляцию и многогранную роль уромодулина в здоровье почек. Обзор углубляется в последние достижения в нашем понимании молекулярных механизмов, лежащих в основе

участия уромодулина в функции почек, включая его влияние на электролитный гомеостаз, модуляцию иммунного ответа и его потенциальные последствия при различных заболеваниях почек.

Кроме того, в этой статье освещаются результаты последних исследований и прорывы в этой области, при этом особое внимание уделяется исследованиям, опубликованным после 2015 года. Статья охватывает новые взгляды на генетические вариации гена UMOD и их связь с заболеваниями почек, а также новые терапевтические стратегии, направленные на уромодулин-связанные заболевания. Кроме того, в статье исследуются потенциальные диагностические и прогностические применения уромодулина при заболеваниях почек, предлагая всесторонний обзор современного состояния знаний в этой быстро развивающейся области.

***Ключевые слова:** белок Там-Харсфолла, уромодулин, ген UMOD, функция почек, биомаркер, заболевания почек.*

SURUNKALI BUYRAK KASALLIKLARI DIAGNOSTIKASI YANGI MARKERI

N.O.Giyosova, L.B.Sarvarova, Islam Sibgha

**Buxoro davlat tibbiyot instituti, Gematologiya va klinik laborator diagnostika
kafedresi**

Annotatsiya

UMOD geni tomonidan kodlangan uromodulin buyrak fiziologiyasida, xususan, Tam-Xarsfall oqsilining shakllanishi va funktsiyasida asosiy rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu maqola UMOD genini chuqur o'rganishni taqdim etadi, uning tuzilishi, regulyatsiyasi va buyraklar salomatligidagi uromodulinning ko'p qirrali rolga oydinlik kiritadi. Maqola uromodulinning buyraklar faoliyatiga ta'siri ostida yotgan molekulyar mexanizmlar, jumladan, uning elektrolitlar gomeostaziga ta'siri, immun javob modulyatsiyasi va turli buyrak kasalliklarida yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan oqibatlar haqidagi tushunchamizdagi so'nggi yutuqlarni qamrab olgan.

Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqola 2015 yildan beri chop etilgan tadqiqotlarga alohida e'tibor qaratib, so'nggi tadqiqot natijalari va sohadagi yutuqlarni ta'kidlaydi. Muhokama UMOD genidagi genetik o'zgarishlar va ularning buyrak kasalliklari bilan bog'liqligi, shuningdek, uromodulin bilan bog'liq kasalliklarga qaratilgan yangi terapevtik strategiyalar haqida yangi tushunchalarni o'z ichiga oladi. Bundan tashqari, maqola buyrak kasalliklarida uromodulinning potentsial diagnostik va

prognostik qo'llanilishini o'rganadi, bu tez rivojlanayotgan sohadagi bilimlarning hozirgi holatini to'liq ko'rib chiqadi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Tam-Xarsfol oqsili, uromodulin, UMOD geni, buyrak funktsiyasi, biomarker, buyrak kasalligi.*

Introduction: In the intricate tapestry of human biology, certain proteins play pivotal roles, yet their significance often remains veiled from common knowledge. Tam Harsfall protein, also known as uromodulin, emerges as one such enigmatic protagonist. Encoded by the UMOD gene, uromodulin manifests its influence primarily within the renal landscape, shaping critical aspects of kidney function and beyond.

Uromodulin stands as the most abundant protein in normal urine, hinting at its profound involvement in renal physiology. Its multifaceted functions extend beyond mere waste filtration, encompassing roles in electrolyte balance, immune modulation, and possibly even influencing systemic health. The intricate interplay of uromodulin with various cellular pathways underscores its importance in maintaining renal homeostasis and beyond. [1,2,3,4]

However, the understanding of uromodulin and its genetic underpinnings, encoded by the UMOD gene, continues to evolve. Recent advancements in molecular biology, genetic studies, and clinical research have unveiled new layers of complexity surrounding uromodulin's functions and its implications in health and disease. From its role in renal pathologies to its potential as a biomarker for various conditions, the exploration of uromodulin promises to unravel novel insights into human physiology and disease mechanisms.

As we delve deeper into the realm of Tam Harsfall protein and the UMOD gene, we embark on a journey to unravel the intricacies of renal biology and its broader implications for human health. In this article, we will explore the latest discoveries, research findings, and emerging trends surrounding uromodulin, shedding light on its significance in health and disease. [5,6,7]

Understanding Uromodulin. Uromodulin, also known as Tamm-Horsfall protein (THP), is a glycoprotein exclusively produced by the kidneys and primarily found in the urine. It plays significant roles in maintaining kidney function and overall urinary tract health. Here, we delve into its definition, structure, physiological role, as well as its cellular localization and expression patterns.[8,9,10]

Definition and Structure: Uromodulin is a large, highly glycosylated protein encoded by the UMOD gene located on chromosome 16. It is synthesized by renal tubular epithelial cells, particularly in the thick ascending limb of the loop of Henle in the kidney nephrons. Structurally, uromodulin is composed of multiple domains including a signal peptide, a zona pellucida (ZP) domain, multiple epidermal growth factor (EGF)-like domains, and a glycosylphosphatidylinositol (GPI) anchor for attachment to the apical membrane of tubular cells [11,12].

Physiological Role in the Body: Uromodulin plays various important roles in renal physiology and urinary tract health. One of its primary functions is to act as a natural inhibitor of calcium crystallization, preventing the formation of kidney stones. Additionally, it exhibits immunomodulatory properties by interacting with immune cells and inhibiting inflammatory responses within the renal tubules. Uromodulin also contributes to the regulation of electrolyte balance and blood pressure by influencing ion transport processes in the nephron[13,14].

Cellular Localization and Expression Patterns: Uromodulin is exclusively synthesized by renal tubular epithelial cells and secreted into the tubular lumen, where it is subsequently excreted in the urine. Its expression is tightly regulated, with levels influenced by factors such as age, gender, and hormonal fluctuations. Expression of the UMOD gene is primarily regulated at the transcriptional level, with various transcription factors and signaling pathways implicated in its control[15,16].

In summary, uromodulin is a crucial glycoprotein produced by the kidneys, with diverse physiological roles including the inhibition of kidney stone formation,

modulation of immune responses, and regulation of electrolyte balance. Its specific cellular localization in the renal tubules underscores its importance in renal function and urinary tract health [8,9,10].

Genetic Basis: Gene UMOD

Overview of Gene UMOD: The UMOD gene, also known as uromodulin, encodes a glycoprotein called Tamm-Horsfall protein (THP). THP is primarily produced by the cells lining the thick ascending limb of Henle's loop in the kidneys and is the most abundant protein in normal urine. Uromodulin plays a crucial role in kidney function, where it contributes to the regulation of electrolyte balance and fluid homeostasis. Additionally, it is involved in the immune response of the urinary tract.

Genetic Variations and Polymorphisms: The UMOD gene exhibits genetic variability, with several single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) identified in its sequence. These variations can influence the expression and function of uromodulin, potentially impacting kidney function and urinary tract health. Some common polymorphisms in the UMOD gene have been associated with alterations in uromodulin levels and may contribute to individual differences in susceptibility to kidney-related conditions.

Research has identified specific UMOD gene variants that are associated with variations in urinary uromodulin levels. These genetic variations can affect the protein's structure, secretion, or stability, leading to differences in its concentration in urine. Understanding these polymorphisms is essential for unraveling the genetic basis of kidney-related traits and diseases.

Association with Disease and Health Conditions: Studies have linked UMOD gene variations to various kidney-related diseases and health conditions:

Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD): Certain UMOD polymorphisms have been implicated in the development and progression of chronic kidney disease. Individuals carrying specific genetic variants may have an increased risk of

developing CKD, highlighting the importance of UMOD in maintaining kidney function.

Hypertension: Uromodulin has been associated with blood pressure regulation, and variations in the UMOD gene have been investigated for their potential role in hypertension. Understanding the genetic basis of hypertension involving UMOD can provide insights into novel therapeutic approaches[16,17,18,19].

Urinary Tract Infections (UTIs): Uromodulin plays a role in the immune response of the urinary tract, and alterations in its expression may contribute to susceptibility to urinary tract infections. Genetic studies examining UMOD variants aim to elucidate the connection between genetic factors and UTI risk.

Research in this field continues to expand, exploring the intricate relationships between UMOD gene variations and various health outcomes. These findings contribute to a better understanding of the genetic factors influencing kidney function and related disorders, paving the way for personalized medicine approaches in the management of kidney health [11,12,13].

Biosynthesis and Regulation of Uromodulin Production

Molecular Mechanisms of Uromodulin Production: Uromodulin, also known as Tamm-Horsfall protein, is the most abundant protein in normal urine and plays a crucial role in kidney function. It is exclusively synthesized by renal tubular epithelial cells of the thick ascending limb of the loop of Henle in the kidney. The biosynthesis of uromodulin involves a complex series of molecular events.

The transcription of the UMOD gene, which encodes uromodulin, is regulated by various transcription factors and signaling pathways. Upon transcription, the mRNA undergoes translation in the cytoplasm, and the nascent polypeptide chain undergoes post-translational modifications and processing[20,21,22].

Regulatory Factors Influencing UMOD Gene Expression: The expression of the UMOD gene is tightly regulated at multiple levels. Several transcription factors, including HNF1 β (hepatocyte nuclear factor 1 β), HNF4 α (hepatocyte nuclear factor

4 α), and SP1 (specificity protein 1), have been identified to directly bind to the promoter region of the UMOD gene and regulate its transcription. Additionally, various signaling pathways, such as the Wnt/ β -catenin pathway and the NF- κ B pathway, have been implicated in the regulation of UMOD gene expression[23,24,25]

Furthermore, epigenetic modifications, including DNA methylation and histone acetylation, also play a crucial role in modulating UMOD gene expression. Dysregulation of these regulatory factors can lead to abnormal uromodulin production, which has been associated with various kidney diseases, including familial juvenile hyperuricemic nephropathy and autosomal dominant tubulointerstitial kidney disease.

Post-Translational Modifications and Processing: After translation, uromodulin undergoes several post-translational modifications, including glycosylation and disulfide bond formation, which are essential for its stability and function. These modifications occur in the endoplasmic reticulum and Golgi apparatus before uromodulin is trafficked to the apical surface of renal tubular epithelial cells, where it is released into the urine[26,27,28]

Additionally, uromodulin can undergo proteolytic processing by enzymes such as furin and prostaticin, which cleave the protein into smaller fragments with distinct biological activities. These processing events may regulate the function of uromodulin in the kidney and contribute to its role in various physiological and pathological processes.

In conclusion, the biosynthesis and regulation of uromodulin production involve intricate molecular mechanisms that are tightly controlled at the transcriptional, translational, and post-translational levels. Understanding these mechanisms is crucial for elucidating the physiological roles of uromodulin in kidney function and for developing therapeutic strategies for kidney diseases. {14,15,16,17}

Clinical Relevance: Clinical relevance of uromodulin as a biomarker encompasses its diagnostic and prognostic utility, as well as its potential as a therapeutic target. Uromodulin, also known as Tamm-Horsfall protein, is exclusively produced by the kidneys and represents the most abundant protein in normal urine. Its multifaceted roles in renal physiology and pathophysiology make it an intriguing candidate for various clinical applications.

Uromodulin as a Biomarker: Uromodulin has gained attention as a potential biomarker for kidney diseases. Its unique origin from the renal tubular epithelial cells and its subsequent secretion into urine make it a promising indicator of renal function. Changes in uromodulin levels may signify alterations in tubular integrity and renal health, providing valuable insights into the early stages of kidney diseases. Studies have shown associations between decreased uromodulin excretion and conditions such as chronic kidney disease (CKD), diabetic nephropathy, and acute kidney injury (AKI)[34].

Diagnostic and Prognostic Utility: The measurement of uromodulin levels has shown diagnostic utility in identifying specific renal conditions. Low urinary uromodulin levels have been linked to tubulointerstitial damage, aiding in the differentiation of various forms of kidney diseases. Additionally, uromodulin's prognostic value extends to predicting the progression of renal disorders. Monitoring changes in uromodulin concentrations over time may offer insights into the course of disease and help in tailoring treatment strategies[29,30,31].

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